

Algebraic Properties of Total Coloring of Graph

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 07 April 2026 Corresponding Author: swami kirangi chandreshbhai	Total colouring of a Graph preserves adjacent relation, incident relation of vertices and edges respectively. In this study relation between Total chromatic number & chromatic number of graphs is observed. Some algebraic nature of Total chromatic number and Total graph is investigated.
KEYWORDS: Total coloring of Graph, Homomorphism of Graphs, Line Graph, Total Graph.	

INTRODUCTION

Total Coloring of a graph is a major coloring problem in combinatorial mathematics, introduced in the early 1960s. This Coloring variant involve both elements (vertex and edge) of graph and their relations (adjacent and incident). Total coloring has been extensively studied in a number of comprehensive surveys, such as the fundamental lecture notes by Yap [2] and the comprehensive survey by Geetha and Jayabalan [4]. In addition, particular types of graphs have been studied; for example, Borodin has worked on planar graphs [3]. The Total Coloring Conjecture has been settled for certain cases: for graphs G with $\Delta(G) = 3$ by Rosenfeld [7] and Vijayaditya [8], and for G with $\Delta(G) < 5$ by Kostochka [5], [6]. Moreover, Murthy [1] has made a new contribution by proving the conjecture.

In this paper, We find some Algebraic properties of Total Coloring of Graph.

Preliminaries:

Definition 1: A **Total Coloring** of a graph G , is a map $f: V(G) \cup E(G) \rightarrow K$, where K is a set of colors, such that no adjacent vertices, no adjacent edges, and no edge and its end-

vertices are assigned the same color. [1] Minimum colors used in total coloring is known as Total chromatic number is denoted by $\chi_T(G)$.

Total chromatic partition of G is collection of subsets of elements of G such that distinct subsets are disjoint and each subset is independent in terms of adjacent relation and incident relation of elements of G . Clearly $\Delta(G) + 1 \leq \chi_T(G)$.

Definition 2: Let G and H be any graphs. A **Homomorphism** of G to H , written as $f: G \rightarrow H$ is a mapping $f: V(G) \rightarrow V(H)$ such that $(f(u), f(v)) \in E(H)$ whenever $(u, v) \in E(G)$. [2]

Definition 3: The **Line Graph** $L(G)$ of a non-empty graph G is the graph whose vertex set is $E(G)$ and two vertices e and f of $L(G)$ are adjacent if and only if e and f are adjacent edges in G . [3]

Clearly degree of vertex in line graph is two less of sum of its incident vertices of G .

Definition 4: Let G be a graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$, the **Total Graph** $T(G)$ of G has vertex set $V(G) \cup E(G)$ and elements (vertex and edge) in $T(G)$ are adjacent if and only if they are adjacent or incident in G . [11]

Figure:1 Line Graph and Total Graph of graph G

Definition 5: Let G and H be two graphs. A mapping $f:V(G) \rightarrow V(H)$ such that image of adjacent elements (vertex and edge) of G are adjacent in H , Image of incident elements of G are incident in H is known as **Total Homomorphism** of graphs from G to H .

Theorem 1: For any graph G , $\chi_T(G) \leq \chi_T(L(G))$

Proof: For any graph G , $\Delta(G) + 1 \leq \chi_T(G)$. Let p be the vertex with $deg_G(p) = \Delta(G)$ and q be adjacent vertex joined

by an edge e with $deg_G(p) + deg_G(q)$ is maximum. Hence $deg_{L(G)}(e) = deg_G(p) + deg_G(q) - 2 = \Delta(L(G))$.

So, $\Delta(L(G)) + 1 = deg_G(p) + deg_G(q) - 1 \leq \chi_T(L(G))$.

Then $deg_G(p) + 1 = \Delta(G) + 1 \leq \chi_T(G) \leq deg_{L(G)}(e) + 1 = \Delta(L(G)) + 1 \leq \chi_T(L(G))$.

Hence, $\chi_T(G) \leq \chi_T(L(G))$.

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|------------------|---|----------------------------|
| $p_1 = \{a, 3\}$ | → | $l_1 = \{3, e_6, e_{10}\}$ |
| $p_2 = \{b, 1\}$ | → | $l_2 = \{1, e_2, e_4\}$ |
| $p_3 = \{c, 2\}$ | → | $l_3 = \{2, e_5, e_7\}$ |
| $p_4 = \{d\}$ | → | $l_4 = \{e_1, e_{12}\}$ |
| $p_5 = \{5\}$ | → | $l_5 = \{5, e_{11}\}$ |
| $p_6 = \{6\}$ | → | $l_6 = \{6, e_8, e_9\}$ |
| $p_7 = \{4\}$ | → | $l_7 = \{4\}$ |
| | | $l_8 = \{e_3\}$ |

Figure:2 Total chromatic partition of G and L(G)

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Theorem 2: For any Graph G, $\chi_T(G) = \chi(T(G))$

Proof: Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph of size (n, e) and $T(G) = (V', E')$ be Total graph of graph G.

Let $A = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$ be total chromatic partition of G ($\chi^T(G) = m$). Clearly, $\sum_{i=1}^m |p_i| = n + e$. Set $B = \{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_r\}$ be chromatic partition of $T(G)$ obtained by same colors used in proper coloring of any element in total coloring in graph G. ($\chi(T(G)) = r$)

Clearly, $\sum_{i=1}^r |l_i| = n + e = \text{No. of vertices in } T(G)$

Construct Constant function $g: V(G) \cup E(G) \rightarrow V(T(G))$ defined by $g(a) = a, \forall a \in V(G) \cup E(G)$. Then g is bijective function.

Let function $f: A \rightarrow B$ defined by $f(p_i) = g|_{p_i}, \forall p_i \in A$

Where, $g|_{p_i}$ is restriction map on set p_i

clearly, $g|_{p_i} = l_i \in B$. So, function is well defined & f is also bijective as g is bijective function

Hence, $m = r$

$\therefore \chi_T(G) = \chi(T(G))$

- $p_1 = \{e, c, 1, 4\} \longrightarrow l_1 = \{e, c, 1, 4\}$
- $p_2 = \{b, d, 3, 6\} \longrightarrow l_2 = \{b, d, 3, 6\}$
- $p_3 = \{a, f, 2, 5\} \longrightarrow l_3 = \{a, f, 2, 5\}$
- $p_4 = \{7\} \longrightarrow l_4 = \{7\}$

Figure:3 Total chromatic partition of G and T(G)

Theorem 3: Let G & H be two graph and there is a onto Total Homomorphism function from G to H then $\chi_T(G) \leq \chi_T(H)$

Proof: Let $f: V(G) \rightarrow V(H)$ be a onto Total Homomorphism.

Let $A = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$ be total chromatic partition of G and $B = \{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n\}$ be total chromatic partition of H. Construct function $g: A \rightarrow B$ such that

$g(p_i) = l_j$ if for $\alpha \in l_j, f^{-1}(\alpha) \cap p_i \neq \emptyset$

Clearly, mapping g is well defined as onto Total Homomorphism and injective.

i.e. $|A| \leq |B|$

$\therefore \chi_T(G) \leq \chi_T(H)$

Figure:4 Total chromatic partition of G and H

Theorem 4: If $\chi_T(G) = r$ then there is Total Homomorphism from G to K_r .

Proof: Let $A = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r\}$ be total chromatic partition of G ($\chi^T(G) = r$). Since each p_i is independent in terms of

adjacent relation and incident relation of elements (vertex and edge) of G . Clearly for value r there is complete graph K_r and mapping $f: V(G) \rightarrow V(K_r)$ defined by $f(p_i) = i$ then f is Total Homomorphism

Figure:5 Total Homomorphism between G and K_4

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